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APPLICATIONS OF COMPOSITE MATERIAL SYSTEMS
TO AVIONIC SYSTEMS PACKAGING

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ABSTRACT

Future avionic packaging designs require design concepts and new materials that reduce weight, increase performance and reliability, and reduce life cycle costs. The Naval Avionics Center (NAC) is investigating and pursuing a total packaging concept that incorporates new material systems into all major aspects of avionic packaging. The NAC Materials Laboratory and Consultants Division in conjunction with the Advanced Technology Division is implementing and guiding a packaging development program that uses advanced materials to advantage in the following areas:

- * Avionic Enclosures
- * Thermal Management
- * Surface Mount Technology
- * Circuit Module Heat Sinks
- * External Stores
- * Embedded Optical Fibers for Communications
- * Diamond Film Investigations (substrates and tooling)
- * Equipment Racking and Consoles
- * Electronic Cable Coverings

The advantages of composite materials are numerous: high specific strengths and moduli; tailorable thermal, electrical, and expansion properties; and adaptability to manufacturing processes. NAC is concentrating on application specific uses of reinforced metal and organic matrix composite materials (MMC and OMC) to meet the packaging constraints of the military environment, espe-

cially the Navy aircraft carrier environment. Prioritized requirements include: reduced weight, electromagnetic protection, thermal management, and thermal expansion/contraction. In addition to these basic "drivers" are included material cost and availability, corrosion potential, manufacturing processing, and repairability. As composite material utilization matures from prototyping to production and fleet deployment, these prioritizations will experience shifts in relative importance.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Avionic packaging must support the Department of Defense goals to maximize aircraft performance and overall weapons system efficiency. The intelligent incorporation of advanced composite material systems with inherently high specific structural and thermal properties will provide new avionic systems with increased performance and reliability, and reduced weight and life cycle costs. Composite material reinforcements and matrices must be selectively chosen to meet structural, thermal, chemical, and manufacturing needs. No particular metal, organic or ceramic composite material system (MMC, OMC, CMC) is best suited for all environmental and manufacturing situations.

Naval aircraft experience harsh environments and weight penalties. Carriers deploy with an embarked air wing that includes both fixed and rotary wing aircraft. The aircraft and their associated avionics are constantly exposed to severe oceanic corrosive and operational stresses. These stresses include high shock loads from launch catapults and arrestment activities, structural and acoustic vibration and shock, thermal loads and maintenance actions. Composite based hardware will combat the adverse impacts of these harsh environments and their associated penalties. This paper will present an overview of specific ongoing NAC efforts to investigate and develop composite avionic hardware components.

2.0 DEVELOPMENTS AND INVESTIGATIONS

High priority developments include: avionic enclosures, circuit module assembly (CMA) heat sink frames, racking and consoles, embedded optical fibers, and diamond filming. These areas of interest provide great impact on avionic packaging with respect to weight reduction and performance/reliability issues. These particular areas are undergoing investigation and development at Naval Avionics and will be reviewed.

Enclosures Experimental 3/4-Air Transport Racking (3/4-ATR) enclosures have been designed and fabricated both in-house and by contracted commercial vendors. NAC in-house units have been fabricated using graphite and fiber-glass reinforced epoxy materials using vacuum bag/autoclave processing. In-house fabrications used low modulus graphite and E-glass reinforced epoxy materials and simple hand layup techniques. These units will be loaded for vibration, shock testing, and will also undergo non-destructive testing (NDT) evaluations.

Enclosures were also procured from ICI Advanced Materials and SPARTA. The unit from ICI Advanced Materials explored the use of thermoplastic materials using flat panel and angle construction. APC-2/AS4 12 inch wide thermoplastic prepreg unidirectional tape and polyetherimide (PEI) adhesive were used for detail fabrication. The enclosure assembly was vacuum bag/autoclave processed. In addition to structural testing, this enclosure will also test a selected metallic coating system for enhanced electromagnetic (EMI) protection.

The SPARTA fabricated enclosure was more complex. This unit was designed to explore the combined use of organic and metal matrix composites within the same enclosure. This project integrated the systems requirements into the design of the avionics enclosure and the materials that make up the enclosure. A 40 percent weight reduction was achieved compared to a similar all-aluminum enclosure. This enclosure design included finned conduction/convection heat exchangers and card holders. Figure 1. illustrates the enclosure (composite enclosure on left).

FIGURE 1. Composite and Aluminum 3/4 ATR Enclosures

Although extended environmental and structural testing has not yet been finished, the resulting design appears to fulfill all functional requirements. The original design goal of incorporating high modulus graphite reinforcing fibers in the card wall heat exchangers for increased thermal conductivity was not met due to an (industry-wide) immaturity in fabricating high modulus fibers three-dimensionally. This goal will be met in FY-92. Current design utilizes SiC/Al.

Development parameters of the MMC/OMC enclosure, in prioritized order include: 1) minimization of weight; 2) maximization of EMI protection; 3) maximization of thermal and structural capability of the enclosure; and 4) minimization of cost. Weight reduction was assigned first priority at this time due to the basic need to minimize weight and associated weight penalties for every component on all aircraft and flight vehicles. Weight minimization is also a necessary prerequisite in upgrading, through retrofitting, existing avionic systems to eliminate or reduce adverse impacts on vehicle performance and to eliminate the need for structural modifications. The typical focus, when upgrading aircraft capabilities, is on increases in electronic systems capabilities (i.e., data processing speed, radar range, jamming strength, etc.). Improved electronic systems generally weigh more and generate higher thermal dissipation loads than the systems they replace.

The employment of composite materials, with greater structural and thermal needs accommodated, will support the design of new systems and the upgrading of older systems with reduced or no weight penalties. In addition to the

TABLE 1. COMPARISON OF COMPOSITE AND ALUMINUM 3/4 ATR DESIGN

	ALUMINUM	COMPOSITE
Frame Assembly Enclosure	10 pieces-4 frame parts and 6 covers	3 pieces - (1) frame and 2 covers
Cardguide (2 required)	Integrated card guide in frame enclosure	1 piece-MMC card guide
Attachments	106 screws and bolts for covers and frames only	54 screws and bolts for cover and frames only
Total Structure Weight (without electronic or attachment components)	5.10 Kg (11.25 lbs)	2.95 Kg (6.5 lbs)
Fabrication Process	Machining of components	Net shape molding

basic weight reduction achieved, enclosure complexity was reduced. Table 1. compares the designs of the composite and aluminum enclosures. Further weight reduction will be effected when planned improvements are accomplished using high modulus graphite card holder heat exchangers and non-metallic hardware (e.g. handles, card clamps, etc.).

Material analytical trade-off studies were conducted. Based on environmental and structural needs for the Naval environment, the general conclusion reached was that the lightest weight 3/4-ATR would result from usage of T-300 low modulus, high strength graphite fibers as opposed to P130X high modulus graphite fibers. A balanced plain weave T-300 cloth prepreg was used for fabrication to provide acceptable mechanical properties and toughness. A range of thermoset and thermoplastic resins were considered for the composite matrix. The resin system chosen was 934 epoxy because of its compatibility with the T-300 fiber, availability, toughness, and low cost. It is also similar to AS4/3501 graphite epoxy combination approved for non-primary structures on F/A-18 aircraft and would, therefore, facilitate acceptance for use by the Navy in this application. Syntactic foam Syncore HG9872 was used as a core material in reinforcing sections in the enclosure and covers. Table 2. compares key properties and features of three leading resin systems with aluminum. EMI shielding requirements were met using two (2) layers of a nickel coated graphite (NCG) mat layer which were co-cured in place during the initial fabrication process.

TABLE 2. COMPARISON OF EPOXY, PEEK AND PPS REINFORCED WITH T-300 GRAPHITE FIBER TO ALUMINUM

Property/Feature	Gr/Epoxy	Gr/PEEK	Gr/PPS	6061-T6 Al (Ref.)
Data Base	Extensive	Fair	Fair	Extensive
Ease of Handling	Good	Acceptable	Acceptable	Good
Moisture Absorption/ Moisture Expansion	Poor to Fair	Fair to Good	Fair to Good	No absorption/ expansion
Toughness Char.	Moderate	Tough	Tough	Tough
Offgassing Char.	Fair	Fair	Fair	No outgassing
T _G -°C	177-232	149	85	N/A
Requires Surface Coating?	Yes	Yes	Yes	No

Data supplied to NAC and SPARTA indicated that two layers of the NCG material, separated by .178 cm (.070 in.) to .025 cm (.010 in.) will provide EMI attenuation in excess of the required 70dB in the range of 0.1 to 10,000 MHz. The cardguide holder/heat exchanger assembly was fabricated from an advanced MMC material containing 30 percent (by volume) silicon carbide particulate reinforcement in an aluminum matrix approximately equivalent to 6063 aluminum alloy. The mechanical properties of the material and the rationale for selection is summarized in Table 3. A match die molding process was used to fabricate the basic frame section of the enclosure and the covers. This method was chosen based on the goal to obtain a uniform repeatable product fabricated by proven techniques that would result in a low cost production electronic enclosure.

TABLE 3. CARDGUIDE MATERIAL DESCRIPTION

MATERIAL PROPERTY	VALUE	RATIONALE
Thermal Conductivity Watts/M ² K BTU ft-hr	235 136	31% increase over 6061 Al resulting in improved heat transfer from internally mounted heat sink to air cooled radiator
Coefficient of Thermal Expansion (CTE) 10 ⁻⁶ /°C 10 ⁻⁶ /°F	14.5 8.0	38% decrease from 6061 Al resulting in a minimization of thermal expansion mismatch between cardguide holder and advanced low CTE heat sink materials
Modulus 10 ⁴ MPa 10 ⁻⁶ pounds/in ²	11.9 17.2	72% increase over 6062 Al resulting in minimization of displacement of cardguide/heat sink interface under loading
Strength MPa 10 ³ psi	393 57	36% increase over 6061 resulting in ability to apply greater compressive loads at cardguide/heat sink interface to improve heat transfer
Density gm/cm ³ lb/in ³	271 .098	No significant increase in density associated with improvement of other properties

3.0 CIRCUIT MODULE HEAT SINKS

Avionic designs experience a trend toward ever-increasing levels of performance, reliability requirements, operational lifetime and thermal dissipa-

tion, with simultaneous reductions in size and weight. As hardware is developed to meet these needs, advanced materials will help realize performance, weight, and cost goals. In the arena of circuit modules, NAC is addressing new materials that meet performance, weight, and cost goals for heat sinking, coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) Surface Mount Technology (SMT) substrates, and coatings. Circuit module heat sink frames using various reinforcements and matrix materials are being investigated to achieve increased thermal conductivity, tailorable CTE, corrosion resistance, and improved manufacturing technologies. Initial studies have shown weight reductions of 40 to 50 percent in experimental SMT CMA's. Experimental Standard Electronic Modules in Format-E (SEM-E) have been assembled using graphite/aluminum (Gr/Al) and graphite/thermoplastic (Gr/TP) composite materials. Compared to the standard SEM-E using a 0.318 centimeters (0.125 inch) thick aluminum frame and double-sided alumina ceramic substrates, the experimentally modeled SEM-E CMA's were thinner and approximately 50 percent lighter. Coupled with lighter weight enclosures, specific improvements in CMA heat sink thermal properties, weight reductions of this nature will enhance avionic packaging concepts. One of the ongoing NAC efforts to improve the capabilities of CMA's is to improve thermal and structural properties of card heat sinks. Part of this effort is NAC contract No. N900163-90-C-0271, titled "Improved Thermal Management Materials for Standard Electronic Module-Format E" to SPARTA. One of the primary objectives of this study is to identify and fabricate SEM heat sink panels with an inplane thermal conductivity greater than 250 watts/meterK (W/mk) and a CTE between 5 and 8 parts/million/K (ppm/K). As knowledge is gained from developments such as these, and materials and processing technologies mature, further levels of improvement will be attained. Three-dimensionally processed reinforcements of high modulus graphite fibers will be used to attain more nearly isotropic materials systems. These improvements will lead to increased reliability and increased Mean Time Between Failures (MTBF). CMA weight savings will result from the use of materials with greater specific thermal conductivity. Using Gr/Al panels as an example, SEM-E heat sink panels 0.178 cm (0.070in.) thick can be fabricated using high modulus fibers that provide a thermal conductivity equivalent or greater than a standard 0.317 cm (0.125 in.) thick monolithic aluminum heat sink and also approximately the same density of the aluminum. Fabrications such as these could effect approximately a 40 percent weight reduction.

Engineering requirements for improved SEM-E heat sink materials at this time are: thermal conductivity greater than 250 W/mK; a planar CTE in the range of 3 to 8 ppm/K; a high modulus to maximize the fundamental natural frequency of the CMA; compatibility with military fluid environments; and the capabil-

ity to meet MIL-STD-202, 454, and 810 requirements for thermal and mechanical shock, vibration, salt fog, humidity, fungus, flammability, and bench handling. Materials under consideration in this particular study are enumerated in Table 1.

TABLE 1. CANDIDATE ADVANCED COMPOSITE MATERIALS

MATERIAL	TYPE
P130X Graphite/Aluminum	Continuous Reinforcement
P130X Graphite/Copper	Continuous Repeat
P120 Graphite/Copper	Continuous Repeat
P130X Graphite/Thermoplastic (PEI)	Continuous Repeat
SiC Particulate/Aluminum	Isotropic Properties
Beryllium Oxide Reinforced Beryllium (Brush Wellman Proprietary Material)	Continuous Repeat
P130X Graphite/Epoxy - Aluminum	Hybrid Material

The results and conclusions of the SPARTA study reinforce NAC general conclusions on other selected materials. Significant improvements in CMA heat sink frame thermal and structural material properties will be achieved through the use of advanced composite materials.

4.0 EQUIPMENT RACKING/CONSOLES

Part of the equation to reduce aircraft weight and increase performance includes equipment installation racking and operator consoles. At this time preliminary work has begun on specific P-3 aircraft racking units, with an emphasis on weight reduction, structural strength and durability, electrical grounding, and manufacturing simplicity. Various material types are being considered. Material systems such as SiC/Al, SiC/Al-Li; graphite/resins, and Kevlar/resins will be analytically evaluated. Representative experimental racking will be fabricated and tested for aircraft qualification. Preliminary studies of a P-3 aircraft and avionic suite indicated the potential benefit of using MMC and OMC materials in avionic enclosures, internal hardware, racking and consoles, and cable shielding. An estimated 680 Kg to 1136 Kg (1500 lbs-2500 lbs) potentially could be removed from such an aircraft.

5.0 COMPOSITE EMBEDDED OPTICAL FIBERS FOR COMMUNICATIONS

Future aircraft will utilize optical fibers embedded in aircraft materials as sensors in what has come to be known as smart skins and structures. A NAC team proposes to extend this concept to the use of embedded optical fibers in light weight composite structures with high specific properties, for avionics modular packaging to achieve avionic and intra-aircraft communications. Material processing technologies, optical fibers, connections, and composite materials (MMC and OMC) are under investigation to design, fabricate and test a composite material chassis and circuit card assembly in which embedded and interconnected optical fibers serve as communication links.

Optical fiber communication links offer wide transmission bandwidth and greater signal carrying capacity while achieving immunity to electromagnetic interference and reduced control system weight. However, optical fibers also have special requirements in reliability and maintainability. Termination methods are complex and connectors have proven difficult to work with. Composite embedded optical fibers are anticipated to be more durable in aircraft environments if composite connector blocks can achieve precise alignment of an optical fiber ribbon array. They are also inherently sensitive to alignment; they demand support and protection. The surrounding composite will provide for both of these.

To date, multimode fibers have been successfully processed in graphite epoxy materials and SEM-E size panels have undergone successful simultaneous vibration and signal transmission testing. Experiments are underway to process fibers in aluminum matrix materials and to develop a usable evanescent connection mechanism between panels simulating a CMA and connector board assembly. Key discussions and technology interchanges are ongoing with numerous facilities developing smart skins and optical fiber technologies, including Naval Research Laboratory, Virginia Tech Fiber and Electro Optics Research Center, The Institute for Aerospace Studies at University of Toronto, the Air Force Astronautics Laboratory at Edwards AFB, and Rutgers University.

6.0 DIAMOND FILMS

Diamond filming for electronic packaging is another new materials area being investigated at NAC. Diamond films will provide increased advantages when incorporated with other composite material systems. Diamond possesses the best room-temperature thermal conductivity (approximately 2000 W/mK) of any

material (approximately five times higher than copper), and also is electrically insulating. In addition, diamond has a very low CTE ($0.8 \times 10^{-6}/K$), a high elastic modulus (160 Msi), is the hardest of all materials, and is highly corrosion resistant. Metal matrix composites in particular, offer increased potential for thermal management (e.g., graphite fiber reinforced aluminum) and low CTE (e.g., SiCp reinforced aluminum) for enhanced surface mount device compatibility. Further improvements in performance and reliability of avionic systems will be achieved through the use of thin layers of diamond film applied to the surface of thermally conductive, low CTE composite panels. For example, a Standard Electronic Module Format-E (SEM-E) module fabricated using a diamond coated Gr/Al heat sink panel would exhibit reduced weight and superior thermal dissipation through the combination of high thermal conductivity graphite reinforcing fibers in aluminum matrix and a highly conductive (thermal) surface layer of diamond. NAC is developing the capability to deposit polycrystalline diamond films using a low pressure deposition process. This will enable the exploitation of the superior properties of natural diamond in the form of a surface coating.

The NAC diamond film program is developing the capability to deposit diamond films on various types and sizes of substrate materials using a microwave plasma deposition system. Initial work has focused on experimenting with diamond deposition on silicon and alumina substrate materials in order to optimize deposition parameters. However, the properties of the deposited diamond films are strongly influenced by the morphology and microstructure of the deposited diamond which, in turn, are dependent on the starting substrate surface morphology. Thus, an investigation of the correlation between substrate surface roughness and the resulting diamond film structure has also been undertaken in an effort to determine the optimum surface finish for producing high quality diamond films. Results thus far on the surface condition of alumina substrate samples have shown the surface to be highly porous and rough, a condition which could not be corrected through polishing. Thus a good quality diamond film could not be produced on such a surface. High density alumina substrates will be obtained in order to further investigate the surface condition/diamond growth phenomenon. Samples of aluminum alloy 6061 with 20 v/o SiCp and 40 v/o SiCp are also being used to study diamond film deposition on metal matrix composites. Preliminary examinations of these surfaces also indicated the presence of excessive surface roughness, even after polishing. It is clear that substantial improvements are necessary for successful diamond film deposition on metal matrix composites.

Work will continue to develop NAC's capability to deposit diamond films for electronic packaging. The goal is to be able to deposit high quality diamond films on metal matrix composites, of practical dimension, that provide high thermal conductivity, low CTE, and low weight.

7.0 CONCLUSIONS

Investigations and developments at NAC show promise in the potential maximizing advantages inherent in using advanced composite materials for avionic structures and CMA components. All aspects of weight reductions, performance and reliability increases and life cycle cost may be advantageously impacted.

8.0 RESUME

Robert Morgan Mr. Morgan graduated from Purdue University in 1968 with a degree in Mechanical Engineering. He is employed at the Naval Avionics Center as Manager of the Electronics Packaging Materials and Processes Branch. Responsibilities in electronic packaging include thermal management, Surface Mount Technology and chemical processing, with special emphasis on advanced material technology. He has system design and integration experience on Navy aircraft and missile platforms. Professional affiliations include ASME, SAE, SAMPE, and AIAA. He is a member of the Advanced Materials Committee for the Indiana Corporation for Science and Technology.

